

D8.2. Dissemination and Communication Plan and Activities Part A

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About ThrombUS+

Deep vein thrombosis (DVT) is the formation of a blood clot within the deep veins, most commonly those of the lower limbs, causing obstruction of blood flow. In 50% of people with DVT, the clot eventually breaks off and travels to the lung to cause pulmonary embolism. Clinical assessment of DVT is notoriously unreliable because up to 2/3 of DVT episodes are clinically silent and patients are symptom free even when pulmonary embolism has developed. Early diagnosis of DVT is crucial and despite the progress made in ultrasound imaging and plethysmography techniques, there is a need for new methods to enable continuous monitoring DVT diagnosis at the point of care.

ThrombUS+ brings together an interdisciplinary team of industrial, technology, regulatory, social science and clinical trial experts to develop a novel wearable diagnostic device for point-of-care, operator free, continuous monitoring in patients with high DVT risk. The device will combine autonomous, AI driven DVT detection based on a novel wearable ultrasound hardware, impedance plethysmography and light reflection rheography for immediate detection of blood clot formation in the lower limb. Activity and other physiological measurements will be used to provide a continuous assessment of DVT risk and support DVT prevention via serious gaming. The aggregated data will drive an intelligence decision support unit that will provide accurate monitoring and alerts. Extended reality will be used to guide experts to design exercises and patients to use the device optimally.

ThrombUS+ is intended for use by postoperative patients in the ward, during long surgical operations, cancer patients or otherwise bedridden patients at home or in care units, and women during pregnancy and postpartum. ThrombUS+ will use big data sets for AI training collected in the project via 3 large scale clinical studies and will validate the outcome in the clinical setting via 1 early feasibility study and 1 multi-center clinical trial.

Deliverable D8.2 Description

Dissemination and communication plan. Output of Task 8.1.

According to the Grant Agreement (GA), D8.2 “Dissemination and Communication Plan and Activities - Part A” will define key messages and target audiences, selecting appropriate tools and channels to meet the information needs of the target audiences. The final version of the deliverable (Part B, delivered on M42) will also include any updates and an outline of related activities during the project.

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Terms and Definitions

Term	Definition
AI	Artificial intelligence
AI4EU	A knowledge-sharing platform dedicated to AI-related projects.
Argos/OpenAIRE	An online machine-actionable tool to facilitate research data management
DMP	Data Management Plan
DVT	Deep Vein Thrombosis
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
EU	European Union
Facebook	Online social networking service for the general public
GA	General Assembly (when within the context of project management procedure)
Google Analytics	A service generating statistics about a website's traffic
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
LinkedIn	Online social networking service for professionals
RDM	Research Data Management
SAB	Stakeholder Advisory Board
SEO	Search Engine Optimization
SlideShare	Slide hosting service
SME	Small and Medium Enterprises
Thrombosis	The formation of a blood clot inside a blood vessel
US	Ultrasound
WordPress	Free and open-source blogging tool and content management system
WP	Work package
X (Twitter)	Online social networking service for the public and professionals
YouTube	Online social and streaming networking service

Executive Summary

The goals of this document are:

- (a) to communicate the plan to increase the European and International visibility of the ThrombUS+ project through various communication initiatives, and
- (b) to communicate the plan to disseminate findings, innovations, and results to stakeholders, which include but are not limited to:
 - the medical device industry and
 - medical care providers.

This document will identify key actors to optimize the project's communication and dissemination material, which will be driven by web and social media, including ThrombUS+ mentions and wider market trends relevant to the project. It will also communicate the editorial strategy (press releases and articles in different EU languages, ThrombUS+ e-newsletter), presentations at public and academic events, training and contests, and participation in conferences.

1. Communication and dissemination strategy

The communication and dissemination strategy is designed to ensure that the ThrombUS+ project's findings and outcomes reach a broad audience, fostering knowledge sharing and collaboration amongst the target audiences using key messages.

Key elements of the **communication strategy** include target audience segmentation, key message development, content planning, and the involvement in and organization of scientific events.

Key elements of the **dissemination strategy** include stakeholder identification and engagement, and thorough and efficient dissemination of research results to stakeholders.

1. Objectives

The communication and dissemination strategy will employ a two-pronged approach: public awareness and stakeholder engagement.

The **communication strategy** aims to increase public awareness of Deep Vein Thrombosis (DVT) and understanding of the importance of early detection. The project's identity, goals, and partners will be promoted simultaneously. Targeted communication will keep the public informed of project progress.

The **dissemination strategy** aims to disseminate research results to stakeholders and encourage open dialogue. This interactive approach will allow for anticipating and addressing potential issues, gathering valuable feedback, and ultimately increasing project visibility.

2. Target audiences

The communication and dissemination plan will cater to a diverse range of target audiences, mainly to the end users (i.e. patients), to medical experts and clinicians, and other stakeholders in the medical device field (Table 1).

The scientific community will be a key focus, including peers in bioengineering, radiology/ultrasound, biotechnology, materials engineering, and mechanical engineering. Additionally, industries relevant to project development will be targeted, such as the medical device market, ultrasound transducer industry, microelectronics industry, and smart textiles and wearables industry. European professional organizations and associations will be included, such as the European Thrombosis and Haemostasis Alliance and the European Alliance for Medical and Biological Engineering and Science, alongside relevant industry associations (Figure 1).

We also target medical doctors, residents, caretakers, researchers, and patients seeking informative content. To ensure broader impact, the plan will also encompass patients and carers, patient organizations, and consumer organizations.

Finally, the general public, media outlets, health policymakers, and regulatory authorities will be engaged to raise public awareness and gain wider support for the project's goals.

Table 1. Target audience segmentation

Target Audience	Description of the Target Group	Objectives	Information Needs	Channels
Medical device industry and related industries	Companies with expertise in biotechnology, wearables, or medical device development	Attract potential industry partners for commercialization of the device	Project goals and milestones, regulatory approach, and timeline	Website, Press releases, Exhibitions, social media
European professional organizations and associations	Health-related organizations with a focus on blood clots or vascular health	Gain support, raise awareness and potentially incorporate the device into future clinical practice	Clinical evidence and benefits of the device, impact on patient outcomes and healthcare costs, alignment with existing DVT management practices	Website, Conferences, Press releases, social media
Medical doctors and researchers	Practitioners specializing in vascular medicine, haematology or emergency care, surgeons, oncologists, obstetricians, gynaecologists, anaesthesiologists, intensive care specialists, other medical practitioners who encounter DVT, and researchers focused on thrombosis/DVT	Engage in the project and its goals	Detailed technical specifications of the ThrombUS+ device, data on accuracy and effectiveness of the device compared to existing methods, information on future clinical trials	Website, conferences, social media
Patients	Individuals at risk for DVT, including those with a history of blood clots, undergoing surgery, or with limited mobility, especially use cases as defined in WP2, or having other risk factors. Related patient organizations.	Raise awareness about DVT and educate benefits about the potential benefits of the ThrombUS+ device	Symptoms and risk factors for DVT, benefits and limitations of the device, timeline for potential availability	Website, conferences, clinical trials, social media
Policymakers and regulatory authorities	Agencies responsible for approving and regulating medical devices in Europe	Secure regulatory approval for the ThrombUS+ device and establish a precedent for AI-powered medical devices	"Compliance-by-Design" approach and its impact on regulatory efficiency, safety and security protocols of the ThrombUS+ device, clinical data and validation studies supporting the device's efficacy	Website, clinical trials, exhibitions

Figure 1. Target audience analysis.

3. Key messages

The key messages in this strategy are motivated by the values of transparency, integrity, clarity, efficiency, and credibility. The goal of these messages is to initiate and enhance relationships with the target audiences while creating opportunities for increased awareness of DVT and project visibility (Table 2).

The project tagline **“Detect early, live better”** will be used on public-facing platforms such as social media banners (Figure 2). The first part of the slogan, “Detect early,” refers to the early detection of DVT, and is intended to appeal to medical professionals; the second part of the slogan, “live better,” refers to the improved patient outcomes as a result of early and accurate DVT diagnosis and is intended to appeal to a general audience.

Figure 2. Indicative images of the ThrombUS+ page on the various social media platforms and the ThrombUS+ banner.

Table 2. Audience-specific key messages

Target Audience	Key Message 1	Key Message 2	Key Message 3
Medical device industry and related industries	ThrombUS+ is spearheading the design of a wearable diagnostic device for point-of-care, operator-free, continuous monitoring of DVT.	The "Compliance-by-Design" approach of ThrombUS+ will streamline regulatory hurdles for complex AI-based medical devices. New opportunities for market access for future complex AI-based medical devices will be created.	ThrombUS+ paves the way for faster market access for future complex AI-based medical devices, thereby shortening the path to patients.
European professional organizations and associations	Up to two-thirds of DVT cases exhibit no clinical symptoms, making early diagnosis challenging. ThrombUS+ addresses the critical gap in early DVT detection with a groundbreaking wearable device.	The international setup of the consortium, in addition to the intensive collaboration entailed in the project, will play a critical role in its success. The interdisciplinary team behind ThrombUS+ fosters collaboration for better DVT management.	ThrombUS+ contributes to a paradigm shift in DVT diagnosis, promoting non-invasive, patient-centric care.
Medical doctors and researchers	ThrombUS+ addresses the critical gap in early DVT detection with a groundbreaking wearable device.	The novel, wearable DVT diagnostic tool, empowers early detection, improving patient care with a point-of-care solution for DVT.	ThrombUS+ fosters collaboration between researchers and clinicians for improved DVT management strategies.
Patients	ThrombUS+ is developing a user-friendly wearable device for DVT detection, potentially saving lives. Stay informed about this potentially life-saving innovation.	The ThrombUS+ wearable device strives to eliminate the silent threat of DVT, offering peace of mind and improving patient outcomes.	ThrombUS+ aims to empower patients with a non-invasive, continuous DVT monitoring solution.
Policymakers and regulatory authorities	ThrombUS+ pioneers a "Compliance-by-Design" approach for complex AI-based medical devices, facilitating market access. Our project sets a valuable precedent for future AI-powered healthcare solutions.	ThrombUS+ contributes to improved public health by addressing the unmet need for early DVT detection. Support innovative solutions that have the potential to save lives and reduce healthcare costs.	ThrombUS+ fosters a collaborative approach to navigating regulatory pathways for future AI-driven medical devices.

4. Tools and channels

4.1. Role of partners

The project partners will play a critical role in WP8, as each partner will use its existing network and audience to increase the visibility of the ThrombUS+ project. As part of their consortium activities, all partners are strongly encouraged to contribute input and provide feedback on the communication and dissemination strategy and execution of deliverables as well as day-to-day communication and dissemination activities.

Specific Partner actions include:

- Promoting the ThrombUS+ website and ThrombUS+ social media accounts through reposting and interacting from partner social media accounts
- Providing information and contributing content about each partner organization in the consortium for the ThrombUS+ website
- Participating in brainstorming and content creation for website content such as “Meet the Partner” posts and social media posts such as “Number of the month” (see Annex)
- Creating awareness on gender balance and on sustainable and equitable innovation (T8.5).

4.2. Social media channel selection

The project's online presence is enhanced by the existence of pages on various, widely used social media platforms, as described in Table 3.

Table 3. Social media channel selection

Target Audience	Description	Link to Project Page
LinkedIn	LinkedIn is a professional networking platform, making it an ideal choice to connect with other professionals, businesses, or organizations in a more formal context.	ThrombUS+ LinkedIn
Facebook	Facebook has a massive and diverse user base and is particularly popular among an older demographic, making it an excellent platform for reaching a broad audience.	ThrombUS+ Facebook
X	X (formerly known as Twitter) is an ideal platform for sharing immediate updates, news, and announcements related to the project. It is also the host of MedTwitter, a popular medical community.	ThrombUS+ X
YouTube	YouTube is ideal for creating and sharing video content, and a preferred platform by doctors, residents, medical students, and patients for information. Furthermore, it can be easily embedded on websites, shared on social media, and integrated into various online platforms.	ThrombUS+ YouTube
SlideShare	SlideShare is intended for wider and seamless dissemination of project-related presentations.	ThrombUS+ SlideShare

4.3. Strategic plan and editorial calendar

The attached strategic plan (Annex) outlines platform-specific actions and editorial guidelines for the project’s participation in the social media networks outlined above. The editorial calendar created and managed by SciGen outlines planned monthly content through M42. The goal of these documents is to provide continuity and ensure consistent quality and quantity of editorial output for the duration of the project [M01-M42].

5. Communication Plan

The ThrombUS+ website serve as the primary means of communication for the project’s progress, results, and outputs. It will host all project-related public information and is intended to meet the information needs of the target audiences.

The project website has been created and can be accessed at thrombus.eu. The details of the project website and project identity can be found in D8.1. The site is being maintained and regularly updated with scheduled content and project milestones, as well as the work plan and list of deliverables. After the conclusion of the project, the site will be maintained for a minimum of 5 years and continue to be updated with project results.

The website will contain:

- All public project reports, publications and presentations, and deliverables files for download
- Links to related projects, news section, etc.

5.1. Internal communication

The website will also have a password-protected internal section to serve as a repository and platform of exchange for project internal communications. Internal communication will be administratively supported by the Project Office of ATHENA Research Centre and will be realized via e-communication, the private section of the website and consortium meetings.

5.2. Communication activities

The communication activities are intended to raise awareness about DVT and promote the Thrombus+ project goals as outlined in section 1.3. The full list of these activities including the breakdown of KPI values and activities descriptions are shown in Table 4.

Table 4. Communication activities.

Activity	KPI	Value	Description	Responsible
Website	Awareness	>5000 visits	The website will be disseminated at relevant scientific conferences, amongst the patients of the 5 participating hospitals, and to the students and staff of participating academic partners and the commercial networks of all industrial partners.	SciGen ATHENA
Flyers	Inform, Promote	>1000 copies	The flyers will be handed out at relevant conferences, industrial exhibitions and via the dissemination networks of all partners.	SciGen All
Newsletter	Inform, Engage	10 newsletters (one every 4 months)	The newsletters will be available as posts on the website and will be emailed to interested parties on a 4-month basis. The newsletters will <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Include project developments. – Feature selected and relevant achievements of the partners. – Summarize achievements in the wider scientific areas related to the project. 	SciGen All
Videos	Awareness	>2000 views	A short video with project proceedings and achievements. It will be available on YouTube and the link will be disseminated via the project website and other social media platforms.	SciGen All
Press Releases	Community Engagement	>2	The project coordinator and all partners will periodically release news and developments of the project in local media to engage society. Press releases will be drafted in English and translated into other European languages to increase audience	SciGen

			reach.	
Social Media	Community Engagement	>1500 followers collectively on all platforms	The project plans presence on LinkedIn, X (Twitter), YouTube, Facebook and SlideShare.	SciGen
Training	Capacity Building	>200 downloads of training material	Training material for capacity building of scientists, medics and patients will be developed and distributed digitally. This will include extended tutorials for high school and university students on modelling for biomaterials design and best practices for biomaterial design and triggering lab experiments.	SciGen All
Conferences	Sharing Intelligence	>200 downloads of training material	The consortium will reach out to relevant stakeholders including healthcare organizations, academia, SMEs, industry, patient groups, to create a cluster of interested parties and discuss advancements of the project and beyond.	All
Data Challenge	Capacity Building	>50 participants	This refers to the Thrombus+ data challenge (T8.3) based on the dataset produced by Clinical Study A (T7.2).	ATHENA SciGen
Organize Events	Knowledge transfer and collaboration	>60 participants	The project will organize at least 1 thematic event. The consortium will present the prototype, its impact, technological and market potential, the plan for joint commercialization, and to achieve and implement green and digital priorities. The participants will learn about the latest global trends DVT detection and management and experience a live product demonstration.	ATHENA SciGen

6. Dissemination Plan

The project website thrombus.eu will be the primary dissemination channel to share project results with stakeholders.

The project website will be disseminated:

- at relevant scientific conferences
- amongst the patients participating in the clinical trials of the 5 partner hospitals
- to the students and staff of participating academic partners and the commercial networks of all industrial partners.

6.1. Dissemination activities

The dissemination activities are intended to clearly articulate and meaningfully distribute the research and project results with Thrombus+ stakeholders. The full list of these activities including the breakdown of KPI values and activities descriptions are shown in Table 5.

Table 5. Dissemination activities

Activity	KPI Value	Description
Project Repository	>100 files with deliverables, manuals, presentations, best lab practices.	All 50 project deliverables will produce public documents, public deliverables will be public and sensitive deliverables will be accompanied by a publicly available executive summary. The repository will also include all dissemination and communication material files (flyers, posters, videos) and all publication files and scientific presentation files.
Publications	>12 publications on project results in scientific journals	Scientific publications will be submitted in peer-reviewed Open Access journals or in subscription-based journals that offer an Open Access publishing option.
Conferences	>12 presentations and posters in scientific conferences	Results will be presented both at scientific meetings and conferences. Example Conferences: Annual Conference of the European Society of Biomaterials; International Symposium on Ultrasonic Imaging and Tissue Characterization, IEEE International Ultrasonics Symposium (next 2025), Congress of World Federation for Ultrasound in Medicine and Biology.
Datasets	1 big dataset published in EOSC with >3000 DVT ultrasound scans	The outcome of Clinical Study A (T7.2).
Exhibitions	>2 participants	HELEXPO (2 years), 2 exhibits during medical imaging conferences. HELEXPO is an International Commercial Exhibition held each year in September in Greece. ATHENA has a permanent presence in the exhibition and ThrombUS+ will be included in its booth. EchoNous also regularly participates in commercial exhibitions held.
Stakeholder Events	4 events, >200 attendees	3 thematic events and 1 event at the European Congress of Radiology.
Feedback Session	>700 patients in the clinical studies B1, C1 and C2	20 doctors, 20 nurses and 10 clinical physiotherapists, from 5 EU countries.
Project Meetings	4 per year	At least 1 physical meeting per year, with bilateral technical meetings as needed.

6.2. Scientific publications and publications of datasets

Scientific publications will be submitted in peer-reviewed Open Access journals or in subscription-based journals that offer an Open Access publishing option, respecting the “Guidelines on Open Access to Scientific Publications and Research Data in Horizon 2020.”

An indicative list of open access journals in which the project plans to publish research findings:

- npj Digital Medicine
- Journal of Thrombosis and Haemostasis
- Circulation
- IEEE Transactions on Ultrasonics, Ferroelectrics, and Frequency Control
- IEEE Transactions on Medical Imaging
- IEEE Biomedical and Health Informatics
- Annals of Biomedical Engineering

Manuscripts will be circulated to all partners in advance of submission and partners will be invited to comment. Notwithstanding this, absolute confidentiality will be enforced so as to not jeopardize individual partners’ or the Consortium’s claim to intellectual property rights.

Within the ThrombUS+ project, multiple datasets will be generated, including Clinical Study data. To achieve higher dissemination levels, the following 4 steps are planned:

1. Implement the DMP (Data Management Plan) among consortium partners to ensure that datasets are compliant with **FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable)** principles.
2. Register ThrombUS+ to the EOSC (European Open Science Cloud) environment. EOSC is an environment where data, tools and services can be published, found, and reused.
3. Explore and operate the AI4EU platform. AI4EU is a knowledge-sharing platform dedicated to AI-related projects.
4. Describe datasets in Argos/OpenAIRE tool and make them available through the EOSC platform.

According to the DOA, the Clinical Study A data set containing ultrasound images from DVT examination will be fully public, further increasing the project’s impact, especially within the scientific community (Figure 3).

Figure 3. Steps for publishing Clinical Study A dataset.

6.3. Stakeholder Advisory Board (SAB)

As part of T8.4, the SAB will be composed of representatives of opinion leaders, regulators, industry, health professionals’ organizations, patients’ organizations, and international associations devoted to the use of mobile technologies to improve health (Table 6). Names and short CVs of persons comprising the SAB are included in D1.1.

Table 6. Explaining the role of the Stakeholder Advisory Board

Group Description	Representatives from various stakeholder groups
Purpose	Provide input, feedback, and guidance Ensure project portfolio alignment with strategic vision and project mission Reflect stakeholder needs, expectations, and interests
Functions	Resolve conflicts among stakeholders Mitigate project risks Enhance communication between industry partners Leverage interdisciplinary collaboration
Key Responsibilities	Advise the project portfolio manager Advise the project portfolio steering committee

Representatives and experts invited to join the SAB will be identified by project partners. Outreach and invitations to join the SAB will be extended by the proximate partner within the Consortium on its behalf, or SciGen if no prior relationship to any project partner exists.

The main goal of T8.4 is to ensure ThrombUS+ potential adopters and EU citizens inform the co-production of the wearable DVT monitoring and prevention system developed in the project. Using a combination of best practice citizen engagement approaches, we will work *with* (instead of for) EU citizens and professionals.

6.4. Stakeholder events

Annual SAB meetings will serve as a discussion platform to consult on different aspects of the project and its progress, and provide feedback and guidance to project partners.

7. Dissemination Activities Monitoring and Reporting

Dissemination activities will be regularly reported internally and officially summarized annually. A second report on the communication and dissemination activities of the project, titled “Communication and Dissemination Plan and Activities - Part B,” will be submitted under D8.4 in M42, along with a report on stakeholder awareness and engagement.

Annex: Social Media Strategic Plan

Overview

An overview of planned tasks and targeted metrics for disseminating and communicating the ThrombUS+ project and results in social media and website are shown in Table 7.

Table 7 – Overview of social media plan.

1	KPIs by M42:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> >1500 followers across all accounts >500 video views >5000 website visits
2	Ongoing Tasks:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Monitoring of all SM channels for DVT news and research updates – Interaction (Like, Follow, Retweet/QT, Comment) with other accounts related to: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> 1 Medical technology 2 Biotechnology 3 Horizon EU 4 Medical research 5 Medical news
3	Other information	March is DVT awareness month

Platform-specific plans

Table 8 – Content posting plans across various platforms.

Platform	Plans
LinkedIn	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Post at least twice per month. – The number of the month post will be a monthly LinkedIn post that shares a relevant number or statistic related to deep vein thrombosis. This is a way to distribute the workload of content creation evenly amongst the project partners while ensuring a steady flow of content for the entire duration of the project (Figure 4).
X (formerly Twitter)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Post circumstantial updates – when there is a meeting, newsletter, breakthrough, etc. – Observe and consistently interact with relevant accounts (such as project partners) and hashtags such as #DVT and #HorizonEU.
Facebook	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Post 1-2 times per month. – Prioritize informational posts, infographics, long-form content that will resonate with a general audience.
Website & e-Newsletter	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Consistency of posts is key to building an engaged audience. – A Meet the Partner post will be a one-time post for each partner on the ThrombUS+ website (thrombus.eu), wherein they introduce their organization, its history, and its role and involvement in the ThrombUS+ project (Figure 4).

Figure 4. Meet the Partner: ATHENA RC is already posted on the thrombus.eu website.

Hashtags

- Use 3-5 per post.
- Combine short-tail and long-tail keywords and hashtags.
- Use trending hashtags when appropriate and relevant.
- Indicative hashtags:
 - 1| #DVT
 - 2| #thrombosis
 - 3| #DeepVeinThrombosis
 - 4| #HorizonEU
 - 5| #HorizonEurope
 - 6| #EarlyDetection
 - 7| #EarlyDiagnosis
 - 8| #MedTech
 - 9| #MedTwitter

Calendars

Table 9. Calendar for the “Number of the Month” post on LinkedIn. The number of the month post will be a monthly LinkedIn post that shares a relevant number or statistic related to deep vein thrombosis or the project. The calendar below shows the partner responsible to provide the number/statistic per month.

Month	Partner	Month	Partner	Month	Partner	Month	Partner
Mar 2024	ATHENA	Jan 2025	GNP	Nov 2025	VERMON	Sep2026	HSV
Apr 2024	KTU	Feb2025	CSS-IRCCS	Dec 2025	Fraunhofer	Oct 2026	VDE
May 2024	VERMON	Ma 2025	HSV	Jan 2026	TELEMED	Nov 2026	MEDEA
Jun 2024	Fraunhofer	Ap 2025	VDE	Feb 2026	EchoNous	Dec 2026	PHAZE
Jul 2024	TELEMED	May 2025	MEDEA	Mar 2026	MEDIS	Jan 2027	PBY
Aug 2024	EchoNous	Ju 2025	PHAZE	Apr 2026	ComfTech	Feb 2027	SciGen
Sep 2024	MEDIS	Jul 2025	PBY	May 2026	TAU	May2027	ATHENA
Oct 2024	ComfTech	Aug 2025	SciGen	Jun 2026	LSMU	Apr 2027	KTU
Nov 2024	TAU	Sept 2025	ATHENA	Jul 2026	GNP	May 2027	VERMON
Dec 2024	LSMU	Oct 2025	KTU	Aug 2026	CSS-IRCCS	Jun 2027	Fraunhofer

Table 10. Calendar for the “Meet the partner” post on the website www.thrombus.eu

The Meet the Partner post will be a one-time post for each partner on the ThrombUS+ website, wherein they introduce their organization, its history, and its role and involvement in the ThrombUS+ project. The calendar below shows the partner responsible to provide the number/statistic per month.

Month	Partner	Month	Partner
Mar 2024	ATHENA	Sept 2025	LSMU
May 2024	KTU	Nov 2025	GNP
Jul 2024	VERMON	Jan 2026	CSS-IRCCS
Sep 2024	Fraunhofer	Mar 2026	HSV
Nov 2024	TELEMED	May 2026	VDE
Jan 2025	EchoNous	Jul 2026	MEDEA
Mar 2025	MEDIS	Sep 2026	PHAZE
May 2025	ComfTech	Nov 2026	PBY
Jul 2025	TAU	Jan 2027	SciGen